

ARTICLE 8

THE RIGHT OF EMPLOYED WOMEN TO PROTECTION OF MATERNITY

With a view to ensuring the effective exercise of the right of employed women to the protection of maternity, the Parties undertake:

- 1. to provide either by paid leave, by adequate social security benefits or by benefits from public funds for employed women to take leave before and after childbirth up to a total of at least fourteen weeks;*
- 2. to consider it as unlawful for an employer to give a woman notice of dismissal during the period from the time she notifies her employer that she is pregnant until the end of her maternity leave, or to give her notice of dismissal at such a time that the notice would expire during such a period;*
- 3. to provide that mothers who are nursing their infants shall be entitled to sufficient time off for this purpose;*
- 4. to regulate the employment in night work of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants;*
- 5. to prohibit the employment of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth or who are nursing their infants in underground mining and all other work which is unsuitable by reason of its dangerous, unhealthy or arduous nature and to take appropriate measures to protect the employment rights of these women.*

Catarina de Oliveira Carvalho/ Luísa Andias Gonçalves

INTRODUCTION

Article 8 of the revised Charter aims at protecting employed women with respect to maternity. For this purpose, it recognizes the right to a maternity leave with pay or adequate benefits along with the right to time off for nursing. It also forbids dismissal during pregnancy and maternity leave, as well as dangerous, unhealthy, or arduous work involving pregnant women, women who have recently given birth or who are nursing their infants, besides regulating night work.

The situations covered by the current article are also protected by other international and European sources, the interplay of which has been described as an “upward spiral”¹ of maternity protection in the labour market. To begin with, the ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183 (2000) has to be highlighted, given that it was based on the revised Charter, even though “it sets more elevated requirements”². It is the updated version of Convention No. 3 (1919), later modified by Convention No. 103 (1952), which had a major influence on the original version of article 8 of the 1961 Charter. The ILO Convention No. 171 (1991), regulating night work, also had relevant impact on article § 8.4 of the Charter³. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) includes the principle of motherhood and childhood protection in article § 25.2. Other UN Treaties also deserve to be mentioned here. On the one hand, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966), whose article § 10.2 calls for special protection “accorded to mothers during a reasonable period before and after childbirth”, including “paid leave or leave with adequate social security benefits”. On the other hand, article § 11.2 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (1979) confers protection to women on the grounds of maternity, namely in case of dismissal or harmful work, along

¹ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, “The Right of Women to Maternity Protection”, in Niklas Bruun, et al. (eds.) *The Employment Social Charter and the Employment Relationship*, Oxford and Portland, Hart Publishing, 2017, p. 310.

² Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 326.

³ See Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3.V.1996, p. 6.

with maternity leave with pay or with comparable social benefits. Finally, at EU level, two main instruments must be emphasized in this context. Article § 33.2 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, which addresses “the right to protection from dismissal for a reason connected with maternity and the right to paid maternity leave and to parental leave following the birth or adoption of a child”, was inspired namely by article 8 of the Charter⁴. And Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992, on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding, whose definition of a female worker has admittedly inspired the interpretation of article 8 of the Charter⁵. As it will be mentioned, these instruments assume noteworthy importance when interpreting the Charter, since the ECSR takes account of the law of the EU for this purpose⁶.

Article 8 of the revised Charter has undergone major changes when compared with its predecessor. In fact, the wording of the heading of article 8 of the Charter of 1961 was merely “The right of employed women to protection”, being “based on a rather paternalistic, protective, restrictive approach to female workers”⁷, in line with other important international conventions in force at that time, namely from the ILO⁸. This was particularly obvious regarding §§ 8.4(a)(b), which limited women’s access to night work in industrial employment, as well as to all other work considered “unsuitable for them by reason of its dangerous, unhealthy, or arduous nature”. Such constraints could be considered gender discriminatory, since they are not applicable to men. As stated by the ECJ⁹, “[a]s far as the aims of protecting female workers are concerned, they are valid only if [...] there is a justified need for a difference of treatment as between men and women. However, whatever the disadvantages of night work may be, it does not seem that, except in the case of pregnancy or maternity, the risks to which women are exposed when working at night are, in general, inherently different from those to which men are exposed”.

Thus, the amendments introduced in article 8 by the revised Charter took into account the developments occurred in community law since 1961, abolishing restrictions applicable to women in general and limiting the scope of this provision to pregnant women, women who have recently given birth or who are nursing their infants. Article 8 received a new heading – “The right of employed women to protection of maternity” – directly inspired by the law of the European Union in order “to ensure full equality between women and men, with the sole exception of the protection of maternity”¹⁰. As KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY pointed out, adding two words to the original title (“of maternity”) has brought “a whole world of change”, “in approach, spirit and substance”¹¹.

This new approach is very close to the so-called “exception” approach, adopted by community law since Council Directive 76/207/EEC of 9 February 1976 on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and

⁴ Explanations Relating to the Charter of Fundamental Rights (2007/C 303/02).

⁵ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, pp. 49-50; Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3.V.1996, p. 6.

⁶ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, pp. 49-50.

⁷ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 308. This paternalistic approach is also underlined by Donna GOMIEN, David HARRIS, Leo ZWAAK, *Convention Européenne des Droits de l’Homme et Charte Sociale Européenne: Droit et Pratique*, Strasbourg, Editions du Conseil de l’Europe, 1997, p. 422, and David HARRIS/ John DARCY, *The European Social Charter*, 2nd Edition, New York, Transnational Publishers, 2001, pp. 128 and 263. According to Nicolas VALTICOS, *Derecho Internacional del Trabajo*, Madrid, Tecnos, 1977, p. 422, during the draft of the 1961 Charter, some Scandinavian representatives opposed to this large scope, defending its limitation to pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants. This proposal, nonetheless, was rejected.

⁸ Namely, Maternity Protection Convention Revised (No. 103, from 1952), which updated the previous Convention No. 3 (1919), Night Work (Women) Convention Revised (No. 89, from 1948), and others regulating dangerous and arduous work, such as Convention No. 45 (1935) on Underground Work (Women).

⁹ ECJ, 25 July 1991, *Tribunal de Police, Illkirch, France v. Alfred Stoeckel*, C-345/89, regarding the general prohibition of night work by women, where night work by men is allowed.

¹⁰ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 50; Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3.V.1996, p. 6.

¹¹ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 308 and footnote 3.

working conditions¹², where legal protection of women during pregnancy and after birth was justified as an exception to the equal treatment principle¹³. And it was also in this view that Council Directive 92/85/EEC was approved¹⁴.

Nevertheless, the association between maternity issues and gender equality is already well established in EU law, mostly due to the interpretation activity of the ECJ, according to which any unfavourable treatment of a woman related to pregnancy or maternity constitutes direct discrimination on grounds of sex, since pregnancy and maternity are gender-specific¹⁵. Later, several references in EU legislation explicitly adopted the same *rational*¹⁶. This reasoning of the CJEU was followed by the ECSR when interpreting the revised Charter, as it will be seen below.

Article 8 relates to several other provisions of the revised Charter. Firstly, as a consequence of what has just been explained, article 8 correlates to article 20 (the right to equal opportunities and equal treatment in matters of employment and occupation without discrimination on the grounds of sex) since it has been perceived as “a special norm” aimed at guaranteeing equal opportunities for women in the labour market, given that the accommodation of the biological differences between men and women (the ability to become pregnant, to give birth and breastfeed) is a precondition of equal treatment¹⁷. In this context, articles § 4.3 and 27 must also be considered due to their connection to sex/gender equality. Secondly, an obvious link must be established with articles 3, § 2.4 and § 2.7 while regulating health and safety at work, dangerous occupations, and night work. Thirdly, a direct association can be established with article 12, regulating the right to social security, because of the maternity benefits recognized by article § 8.1¹⁸.

Regarding the personal scope of article 8 of the Charter, it seems to be limited by its own wording to “employed women”. That is, to women who have an employment relationship, including civil servants. According to the ECSR, self-employed women are excluded¹⁹. It is not clear if a (third category) worker must be included²⁰. On the other hand, as will be seen below, the ECSR gives special attention to the so-called atypical forms of employment, protecting part-timers, temporary and fixed-term employees, as well

¹² Repealed by the Recast Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation.

¹³ This is clearly stated in article § 2.3: “This Directive shall be without prejudice to provisions concerning the protection of women, particularly as regards pregnancy and maternity”. A more detailed analysis of this “exception approach” to the topic of maternity protection *vis a vis* the gender equality principle in employment and occupation can be traced at Maria do Rosário Palma RAMALHO, “Reconciling Family and Professional Life and the Gender Equality Principle in Employment”, *European Gender Equality Law Review*, no. 2, 2009, pp. 10 ff.

¹⁴ See Maria do Rosário Palma RAMALHO, *cit.*, p. 10.

¹⁵ E.g. ECJ, 5 May 1994, *Habermann-Beltermann*, C-421/92; ECJ, 14 July 1994, *Carole Louise Webb*, C-32/93; ECJ, 30 April 1998, *Evelyne Thibault*, C-136/95; ECJ, 3 February 2000, *Silke-Karin Mahlburg*, C-207/98; ECJ, 4 October 2001, *Tele Danmark A/S*, C-109/00. For further developments, see CARVALHO, Catarina Oliveira, “Informações Relativas ao Estado de Gravidez e (Não) Contratação de Trabalhadora Grávida para o Exercício de Atividades Proibidas ou Condicionadas Face à Jurisprudência do Tribunal de Justiça das Comunidades Europeias (TJCE)”, in *O Direito Material e Processual do Trabalho dos Novos Tempos – Estudos em Homenagem ao Professor Estêvão Mallet*, São Paulo, LTr, 2009, pp. 94 ff.

¹⁶ E.g. article § 2.2(c) of the Recast Directive 2006/54/EC: “For the purposes of this Directive, discrimination includes: (c) any less favourable treatment of a woman related to pregnancy or maternity leave within the meaning of Directive 92/85/EEC”.

¹⁷ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, pp. 308-309. The same view is shared by Karin LUKAS, *The Revised European Social Charter – An Article by Article Commentary*, Camberley, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2021, p. 134. Still, as the first Author explains, this inclusion on the list of equality provisions of the Charter is often forgotten due to, on the one hand, “its ‘protective pedigree’ inherited from its 1961 predecessor” and, on the other hand, “the demanding financial obligations, which are far from characteristic of equality provisions that are normally negative”.

¹⁸ For further correlations, see Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 311, and Karin LUKAS, *cit.*, p. 134.

¹⁹ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

²⁰ The ECSR has highlighted that woman working at home are included. ECSR, Conclusions 2019, Italy. In some countries (e.g. Portugal), homeworkers are not considered employees but rather workers or self-employed. This reference to women working at home might expand the scope of this provision to workers, and not only employees.

as migrant workers and employed family members²¹. Special employment relationships, such as domestic employees, are also consistently considered²².

The subsequent analysis follows closely the structure of article 8, identifying each of its numbers individually, namely: the right to maternity leave with adequate income (§ 8.1), the prohibition of dismissal during pregnancy and maternity leave (§ 8.2), the right to time off for nursing (§ 8.3), employment of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants in night work (§ 8.4), and employment of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants in unsuitable work, by reason of its dangerous, unhealthy or arduous nature (§ 8.5), ending with brief conclusion remarks that aim to prospect future interpretive developments in the light of the reciprocal interactions between the ESC (rev) and EU law.

I. § 8.1 – RIGHT TO MATERNITY LEAVE WITH ADEQUATE INCOME

A. LEAVE LENGTH

At the time of childbirth, all categories of employed women – both in the private and public sectors – shall be guaranteed the right to a leave of at least 14 weeks, that can be spread before and after delivery. The scope is “both to grant employed women protection in the case of maternity and to reflect a more general interest in public health, i.e. the health of the mother and child”²³.

In the Charter of 1961 this period was only 12 weeks. The extension of the leave to 14 weeks is consistent with the period provided by the European Code of Social Security Revised (article § 56.2)²⁴. It is also aligned with Directive 92/85/EEC (article 8), and ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183 (article 4).

The maternity leave must be guaranteed by law, being customary rights insufficient to comply with this obligation²⁵, or even collective agreements alone²⁶. It must be regulated as a maternity leave and not as a sick leave²⁷, including when the child is stillborn²⁸.

Even so, national law may authorize women to opt for a shorter period of maternity leave. National legislation must recognize women the right to use all or part of the maternity leave, ensuring by means of a scheme of benefits set at an adequate level that they freely choose to use it in full, if that is their wish, forcing the employer to respect that choice. As long as this is granted, national law may admit that women choose to shorten the period of maternity leave²⁹. That is, for example, the case of Portugal, whose domestic law allows women to choose not to use the total period of maternity leave³⁰.

However, the ECSR also considers that a minimum period of cessation of work must be taken after the childbirth to avoid practices that infringe the aim of this provision. This means that a compulsory

²¹ David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, pp. 128-129 and 132; Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 309.

²² E.g. ECSR, Conclusions 2019, Italy.

²³ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1; Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 116.

²⁴ Karin LUKAS, *cit.*, p. 135.

²⁵ ECSR, Conclusions III (1973), Statement of interpretation on Article § 8.1.

²⁶ Conclusions IV, United Kingdom. See, on this issue, Donna GOMIEN, David HARRIS, Leo ZWAAK, *cit.*, p. 421; David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, p. 129; Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 312.

²⁷ Conclusions XII-1, Greece; Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 116.

²⁸ Conclusions XII-1, Greece.

²⁹ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1.

³⁰ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Portugal.

maternity leave of no less than six weeks must be implemented³¹. In fact, despite accepting that national law may permit women to opt for a maternity leave shorter than 14 weeks, the ECSR considers that women shall be guaranteed six weeks' leave after the birth of the child. This period of six weeks shall be mandatory, binding both the employer and the employee³². The possibility to waive the leave in favour of the father is, therefore, only admitted with respect to the period after the compulsory six weeks postnatal leave³³. This interpretation was held consistently by the ECSR until 2011³⁴, in spite of some dissenting opinions that advocated women's freedom of choice over how much leave to take³⁵.

Since 2011, case law has progressively changed, adjusting to international and European law³⁶. The ECSR has accepted that the guarantee of the enjoyment of the postpartum period by women can be achieved by means other than the legal determination of compulsive maternity leave. It is demanded that, in such cases, national law provides "adequate legal safeguards" that assure women are not pressured to shorten their maternity leave, or, in other words, that women really choose freely when to return to work after childbirth³⁷. These alternative ways to ensure the effective enjoyment of six weeks of leave after giving birth, whenever that is women's will, may be, for example, legislation against discrimination at work based on gender and family responsibilities, the existence of agreements with social partners on the question of postnatal leave that protects the free choice of women, or additional protection provided by collective agreements. Furthermore, the ECSR's conclusions about this issue usually require an analysis of the general framework surrounding maternity, such as looking for the existence of other paid parental leaves and finding what is the proportion of women taking less than six weeks postnatal leave³⁸.

For example, when analysing Slovenia's national law, the ECSR considered that, despite the absence of a mandatory period of six weeks of paid leave, the other guarantees offered (prohibition of workers' discrimination on grounds of pregnancy, maternity and parental leaves, together with sanctions against employers who commit such discrimination, paternity and childcare paid leaves) were enough to ensure that women were not pressured to waive their rights connected to maternity leave³⁹. Similarly, in Sweden the law also does not fix a compulsory post-natal leave of at least six weeks. Still, the ECSR was able to conclude that 99% of women in Sweden use their whole maternity leave and legislation provides enough protection against hostile treatment from an employer connected to maternity or parental leave. Furthermore, "it noted that parental leave, which includes maternity leave, affords both parents a right to thirteen months' paid leave (80% of their previous income) to be shared between them as they wish and that the level of maternity benefits is of an adequate level to avoid economic pressure on women to return to work early". Plus, "many collective agreements in both the public and the private sectors provide that the employer pays 10% extra under the ceiling (i.e., workers receive 90% income as parental benefit)

³¹ ECSR, Conclusions VIII (1984), Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1; Conclusions XIX-4 (2011), Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1; Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1.

³² In Conclusions 2019, Azerbaijan, the ECSR concluded that the situation was not in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter "on the grounds that it has not been established that the right to compulsory maternity leave is guaranteed".

³³ Conclusions XIII-5, Portugal.

³⁴ For further developments, see Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, pp. 310-312.

³⁵ E.g. Dissenting opinion of M. Mikkola on Article § 8.1 (Conclusions 2005, Sweden); Dissenting opinion concerning Article § 8.1 by Fritz Fabricius (Conclusions VIII, 1984).

³⁶ See Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, pp. 314-315; ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Statement of interpretation on article § 8.1. According to Directive 92/85/EEC (article § 8.2), maternity leave must only include a compulsory period of at least two weeks. On the other hand, ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183 (article 4) stipulates a compulsory period of six weeks after childbirth, but admits otherwise when "agreed at the national level by the government and the representative organizations of employers and workers".

³⁷ Conclusions 2011, Statement of interpretation on article § 8.1. In Conclusions 2019, Hungary, the ECSR considered that the situation was not in conformity with article § 8.1 on this point on the grounds that it had not been established that there were, "in law and in practice, adequate safeguards to protect employees from pressure to take less than six weeks' postnatal leave". The same happened in Conclusions 2019, Ukraine.

³⁸ Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.1; Conclusions 2011 and 2019, Ireland; Conclusions 2015, Slovenia, Hungary, Latvia and Russian Federation; Conclusions 2019, Hungary and Russian Federation.

³⁹ Conclusions 2015, Slovenia. For other analyses on this matter, see Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Latvia and Lithuania.

and up to 90% above the ceiling⁴⁰. Based on this scenario, the ECSR concluded that Swedish law is in conformity with the ESC (rev)⁴¹.

B. LEAVE PAYMENT

Under article § 8.1 of the ESC (rev), it is mandatory that during their maternity leave women get an economic compensation. This payment can assume different modalities: a paid leave, in which the employer continues paying the wage to their employee despite the absence of work activity; social security benefits; or alternative benefits from public funds. Parties are free to choose the modality of payment, or a combination thereof, provided that the level of economic compensation is adequate.

Similar solutions are provided by Directive 92/85/EEC (article § 11.2⁴²) and ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183 (article 6). Nevertheless, the ILO Convention establishes that benefits “shall be provided through compulsory social insurance or public funds, or in a manner determined by national law and practice”. As a rule⁴³, the employer shall not be individually liable for the direct cost of such monetary benefits, since this option can backfire resulting in the discrimination of women at work, and can lead to payment difficulties⁴⁴.

1. Qualifying period

In most countries, maternity benefits are financed by social security, and national law can make entitlement to payment depend on a minimum period of employment and/or contributions. Nevertheless, the conditions imposed for access to the payment cannot be excessive⁴⁵. It is important, in this matter, to make clear if qualifying periods allow for some interruptions in the employment record⁴⁶. For instance, the ECSR concluded that the situation in Greece is not in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter “on the grounds that periods of unemployment are not taken into account when calculating the qualifying periods required to be entitled to maternity benefits”⁴⁷.

With respect to Albania, the ECSR concluded for non-conformity, since Albanian national law demands for a twelve-month contribution period prior to pregnancy in order to be entitled to maternity benefits, corresponding this period to the last full calendar year preceding the year during which maternity benefits are paid, including periods of unemployment⁴⁸.

⁴⁰ Conclusions 2015, Sweden.

⁴¹ A different interpretation had been held, regarding Sweden, in Conclusions 2005.

⁴² “[I]n the case referred to in Article 8, the following must be ensured: (a) the rights connected with the employment contract of workers within the meaning of Article 2, other than those referred to in point (b) below; (b) maintenance of a payment to, and/or entitlement to an adequate allowance for, workers within the meaning of Article 2; 3. the allowance referred to in point 2 (b) shall be deemed adequate if it guarantees income at least equivalent to that which the worker concerned would receive in the event of a break in her activities on grounds connected with her state of health, subject to any ceiling laid down under national legislation; 4. Member States may make entitlement to pay or the allowance referred to in points 1 and 2 (b) conditional upon the worker concerned fulfilling the conditions of eligibility for such benefits laid down under national legislation”.

⁴³ Except where: “(a) such is provided for in national law or practice in a member State prior to the date of adoption of this Convention by the International Labour Conference; or (b) it is subsequently agreed at the national level by the government and the representative organizations of employers and workers.

⁴⁴ Nicolas VALTICOS, *cit.*, pp. 412 and 422.

⁴⁵ According to Directive 92/85/EEC (article § 11.4), “Member States may make entitlement to pay or the allowance referred to in points 1 and 2 (b) conditional upon the worker concerned fulfilling the conditions of eligibility for such benefits laid down under national legislation. These conditions may under no circumstances provide for periods of previous employment in excess of 12 months immediately prior to the presumed date of confinement”.

⁴⁶ Conclusions 2015, p. 6; Conclusions 2019, Armenia and Hungary.

⁴⁷ Conclusions 2019, Greece.

⁴⁸ Conclusions 2011 and 2019, Albania.

In Azerbaijan, the qualifying period required to receive maternity benefits is only six months. Still, unemployment periods are not taken into account for this qualifying period, which led the ECSR to conclude that the situation in Azerbaijan was not in conformity in this regard⁴⁹. However, in Conclusions 2019, Azerbaijan stated that, when assessing this six-month period, interruptions in a woman's employment record – such as periods when she receives pension or unemployment benefits, periods of paid engagement in Civil Service or periods of lawful employment abroad – are included in her general employment record and, therefore, taken into account in the assessment of the qualifying period for maternity benefits. Consequently, the ECSR considered the situation in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter in this respect.

Another example is the Hungarian legislation, which demands 365 days of contributions during the previous two years before the birth. The birth must take place while the person is insured, or within 42 calendar days of its expiry (28 days if the person receives sickness benefit) or while in receipt of accident benefit. This period was considered “rather lengthy” by the ECSR⁵⁰. Yet, that was not enough for the ECSR to conclude for non-conformity. Instead, it requested clarifications on “how such qualifying period is calculated and, in particular, whether interruptions in the employment record are taken in account as contributory periods”. Moreover, the ECSR asked for statistical data on women who are employed but do not qualify for pregnancy-confinement benefits, as well as information on the respective allowances available.

2. Adequate level of protection

The level of benefits shall be sufficient to allow women to freely choose to take up the full leave⁵¹. As for what is considered “adequate social security benefits” or “adequate benefits from public funds”, the ECSR stated that “[i]n case of continued payment of wages or earnings-related benefits, these shall be equal to the previous salary or close to its value, and not be less than 70% of the previous wage”⁵². As a result, the level of maternity benefits in the Slovak Republic was considered insufficient in 2015, since it only corresponded to 65% of the worker's salary⁵³. Regarding Turkey, the ECSR also concluded that the regime especially applicable to women employed in the press sector was not adequate, once these women, when on maternity leave, were only entitled to the payment of half of their salary by their employer⁵⁴.

Furthermore, for the benefit to be adequate it shall not fall below 50% of the median equivalised income. When the benefit in question stands between 40% and 50% of the median equivalised income, other benefits, including social assistance and housing, will be considered. On the contrary, “if the level of the benefit is below 40% of the median equivalised income, it is manifestly inadequate and its combination with other benefits cannot bring the situation into conformity with article § 8.1”⁵⁵.

⁴⁹ Conclusions 2015, Azerbaijan.

⁵⁰ Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Hungary.

⁵¹ David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, p. 131.

⁵² Conclusions 2015, p. 6.

⁵³ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Slovak Republic. Nevertheless, the amount of maternity benefits increased from 65% to 75% of the employee's salary (Conclusions 2019) and is now in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter on this point. In Conclusions 2019, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the ECSR also considered that the situation is not in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter on the grounds that maternity benefits are inadequate in certain parts of the country. The same happened in Conclusions 2019, Ireland, where the ECSR concluded that the situation was not in conformity with article § 8.1 “on the grounds that the amount of maternity benefit was manifestly too low in the private sector”.

⁵⁴ Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Turkey.

⁵⁵ Conclusions 2019, Andorra; Conclusions 2019, Armenia. In Conclusions 2019, Moldova, although maternity benefit is equal to 100% of the average monthly wage, the ECSR declared the non-conformity of domestic legislation “since the minimum wage in the public sector is lower than the national subsistence level”. A similar situation was identified regarding the Russian Federation (Conclusions 2019), where “the minimum wage is less than the minimum subsistence level during the reference period”, which means that “the minimum amount of maternity benefits is manifestly too low”.

In Serbia, the regulation raised some doubts. Women with at least six months of continuous insurance coverage, when on maternity leave, get a compensation corresponding to 100% of previous earnings. However, women insured for more than three but less than six months only get a payment corresponding to 60% of the salary, and women insured for less than three months have the right to a compensation corresponding to 30% of the salary. In order to clarify the situation, the ECSR asked the next report to indicate the criteria for entitlement to maternity benefits, in particular whether interruptions in the employment record are taken into account in the calculation of the qualifying period, and to provide statistical data on the proportion of women getting less than 70% of their previous salary as maternity benefits⁵⁶.

In its 2015 Conclusions, the ECSR also noted that, under Cyprian legislation, maternity allowance was “still based on the wages earned in the previous insurance contribution year, instead of those earned in the months closer to maternity leave”. Regarding this, the ECSR did not consider Cyprian national law to fail to conform with the Charter, but asked for the next report to provide information about employed women who do not qualify for maternity allowance⁵⁷.

3. Maximum and minimum limits

A ceiling on the amount of compensation for high salary earners is not, in itself, contrary to Article § 8.1⁵⁸. As we can read in 2017 Conclusions apropos Turkish domestic law, “[v]arious elements are taken into account in order to assess the reasonable character of the benefit reduction, such as the upper limit for calculating benefit, how this compares to overall wage patterns and the number of women in receipt of a salary above this limit”⁵⁹.

Minimum rate of compensation shall not fall below the poverty threshold defined as 50% of median equivalised income, calculated on the basis of the Eurostat at-risk-of-poverty threshold value⁶⁰. Irish legislation was considered as non-conforming with article § 8.1 of the Charter in 2011. In fact, despite a rate of 80%, maternity benefits were subject to maximum and minimum rates, both considered too low when compared to the annual at-risk-of-poverty threshold in Ireland⁶¹.

II. § 8.2 – PROHIBITION OF DISMISSAL DURING PREGNANCY AND MATERNITY LEAVE

A. PERSONAL SCOPE

All categories of employed women – both in the private and public sectors – benefit from the prohibition of dismissal from the time they notify the employer of their pregnancy until the end of maternity leave, including special employment relationships such as domestic employees, women working at home⁶², and seafarers⁶³.

⁵⁶ Conclusions 2015, Serbia. The report related to the 2019 Conclusions failed to answer this question, so the ECSR repeated it.

⁵⁷ Conclusions 2015, Cyprus.

⁵⁸ Conclusions 2015, p. 6. Directive 92/85/EEC (article § 11.3) also allows maternity benefits to be subject to the applicable national ceiling for sick benefits.

⁵⁹ Conclusions 2017, Turkey.

⁶⁰ Conclusions 2015, p. 6.

⁶¹ Conclusions 2011, Ireland. From January 2014, “a single weekly payment of €240 was paid to qualifying persons, with the amount paid no longer dependent on income level”. The ECSR recalled that the maternity benefit must be equal or close to the normal salary, i.e. at least 70% of the person’s previous earnings, and concluded that the situation was not in conformity with article § 8.1 of the Charter “on the grounds that the amount of maternity benefit of female employees in the private sector is manifestly too low”.

⁶² Conclusions I, Italy.

⁶³ ECSR, Conclusions XIII-4, Greece.

The prohibition applies equally to women on fixed-term and open-ended contracts⁶⁴. Still, this does not forbid the expiry of fixed-term contracts on the agreed expiry date⁶⁵. Nevertheless, the ECSR recognizes that the expiry of such contracts during the absence on maternity leave might deprive this prohibition of its effects. Consequently, it frequently asks the State parties to provide figures on the proportion of women on fixed-term contracts “outside the specific and traditional instances justifying their use” and their effects on the protection of women employees while on maternity leave⁶⁶.

B. DISMISSAL PROHIBITION PERIOD

In the 1961 Charter, article § 8.2 dictated that Contracting Parties had “to consider it as unlawful for an employer to give a woman notice of dismissal during her absence on maternity leave or to give her notice of dismissal at such a time that the notice would expire during such absence”. The ECSR considered, then, that “notice of dismissal as such was not incompatible with the Charter provided that the period of notice and any procedures were suspended until the end of the leave”. It also believed that “the same rules governing suspension of the period of notice and procedures during maternity leave must apply in the event of notice of dismissal prior to maternity leave, irrespective of the length of the period of notice”⁶⁷.

The Revised Charter enlarged the prohibition period, anticipating its beginning to the moment when the employer is notified about the pregnancy. Its ending remains the same: the end of the maternity leave. During this period, two things must be prevented: that a woman is given a notice of dismissal; and that a previous notice of dismissal given to a woman comes to an end, expiring. If one of them happens, it shall be sanctioned as unlawful⁶⁸.

The aim is to protect women during pregnancy and maternity leave against the economical and psychological effects of dismissal and safeguard their financial security and security of employment⁶⁹, preventing discriminatory dismissals due to pregnancy⁷⁰.

As it happened with reference to the 1961 Charter, the mere existence of the notice of dismissal itself should not be considered as non-conform with the Charter, as long as it comes with the prevision of suspension of the period of notice and any procedures until the end of the maternity leave⁷¹.

Similar dismissal prohibitions can be found in article 10 of Directive 92/85/EEC, as well as in article 8 of ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183, although the scope of the admitted exceptions may vary.

C. EXCEPTIONS TO THE DISMISSAL PROHIBITION

⁶⁴ Conclusions XIII-4 (1996), Austria; Conclusions 2019, Latvia and Italy.

⁶⁵ ECSR, Conclusions XV-2, Cyprus; Conclusions 2019, Italy.

⁶⁶ ECSR, Conclusions XV-2, Cyprus, Malta and Slovak Republic.

⁶⁷ Conclusions XIII-4.

⁶⁸ In Conclusions 2019, Albania, the ECSR considered that the situation was not in conformity with article § 8.2 of the Charter, since dismissal was possible during pregnancy, before claiming maternity benefits. Therefore, “the existence of adequate protection against unlawful dismissal during pregnancy has not been established”.

⁶⁹ Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Slovak Republic.

⁷⁰ David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, p. 133; Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 317.

⁷¹ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 117.

In Conclusions I⁷², the ECSR interpreted article § 8.2 of the Charter of 1961 declaring that its prohibition was not absolute. The same interpretation is followed regarding the revised Charter⁷³, and these exceptions are now explicitly incorporated in the Appendix to the Charter, including namely the following situations⁷⁴:

- (a) an employed woman has been guilty of misconduct which justifies breaking off the employment relationship⁷⁵;
- (b) the undertaking concerned ceases to operate;
- (c) the period prescribed in the employment contract has expired⁷⁶.

Since the aim of the protection is to ward off discriminatory dismissals by reason of pregnancy, the ECSR accepts that in some cases women can be given notice of dismissal or see the notice period expire between the moment they notify their employers of their pregnancy and the end of maternity leave, as long as such discriminatory bias is absent.

Still, exceptions shall be strictly interpreted, as stated by the ECSR in many different cases⁷⁷.

Dismissals for objective reasons independent from the person of the employee dismissed are not *per se* allowed. For instance, the inclusion of pregnant women in collective redundancies⁷⁸ or the abolition of their job on economic, market, technological or structural grounds⁷⁹ were found in breach of the Charter. Also, the dismissal of a pregnant woman in case of relocation of the undertaking where she works, if she does not follow the company, was not accepted as an admissible exception to the prohibition stated by article § 8.2⁸⁰. The same goes to legislation according to which a pregnant employee can be dismissed in case the work post she is occupying was previously occupied by a person who was illegally dismissed and must be reintegrated⁸¹.

Even objective reasons that are related to the person of the employee, as it happens in cases of unsuitability for the functions performed⁸² or failure to meet the work objectives⁸³, are considered unacceptable. The ECSR also understood that “the employee’s inability to perform her work for reasons related to her health is not a circumstance which authorises dismissal under Article § 8.2 of the Charter”⁸⁴.

Finally, dismissal for subjective reasons, namely of a disciplinary nature, must imply serious fault on the part of the employee (e.g. “non-conformity to the instructions of the employer”, “neglected performance of duties” and “repeated unauthorised absence from work”⁸⁵). For instance, the ECSR considered that the mere “employer's loss of trust in the employee” is “couched in terms that are too vague and can

⁷² Conclusions I, p. 51.

⁷³ Conclusions 2011, Bulgaria, Ireland and Italy; Conclusions 2019, Bulgaria, Ireland.

⁷⁴ Conclusions I, Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.2; Conclusions 2019, Albania.

⁷⁵ Conclusions X-2 (1990), Spain.

⁷⁶ Conclusions 2005, Estonia.

⁷⁷ Conclusions 2011 and 2019, Bulgaria; Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Lithuania; Conclusions 2019, Albania.

⁷⁸ Conclusions 2011, Ireland. In Conclusions XIII-4, Spain, the ECSR states that a collective dismissal (based on economic or technical reasons or for reasons relating to organisation and production) “could only correspond to the grounds allowed by the Committee where the undertaking in question ceased to operate”.

⁷⁹ Conclusions XIII-3 and XIII-5, Portugal. The suppression of jobs on objective structural, technological or economic grounds concerning the company may in principle only overrule the dismissal prohibition “where the company itself is ceasing its activities”.

⁸⁰ Conclusions XVII-2, Czech Republic; Conclusions 2011 and 2019, Bulgaria; Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Slovak Republic.

⁸¹ Conclusions 2011, Bulgaria.

⁸² Conclusions XIII-3 and XIII-5, Portugal.

⁸³ Conclusions 2019, Montenegro.

⁸⁴ Conclusions 2015, Lithuania.

⁸⁵ Conclusions XIII-1, Greece (examples based on Greek case law).

potentially lead to abuse”⁸⁶. The same goes for the non-compliance with the obligations laid down in law, collective agreements, or employment contract⁸⁷. Even in cases in which the employment contract will be terminated following a court decision that prevents the employee from continuing work, or is the consequence of the fact that an employee is deprived of special rights to perform certain work in accordance with a procedure prescribed by law, or happens upon request of bodies or officials authorized by law, the ECSR understands that the legitimation of those exceptions depends on the way such provisions are interpreted and applied⁸⁸. Thus, further guarantees might be needed to carry out the protection granted by the Charter.

On the contrary, an exception according to which a woman can be dismissed (during the period of the general prohibition previewed on article § 8.2) if her trial period has been unsuccessful, and she is protected against discrimination in that situation, was accepted by the ECSR⁸⁹. Also, the liquidation of the company, the bankruptcy of the employer⁹⁰, the expiry of the contract on the death of the employer if the contract was concluded for the purpose of providing services specifically to this person⁹¹, a criminal judgment preventing the employee from continuing her work⁹², or the employee losing through her own fault the necessary certificates to carry out her work⁹³, are deemed acceptable.

D. CONSEQUENCES OF UNLAWFUL DISMISSAL

1. Reinstatement

An employee dismissed in breach of article § 8.2 of the Charter must have the right to take their case before the courts or other independent judicial organs, and demand for legal remedies.

If an employer dismisses a woman in contradiction to the prohibition related with article § 8.2 of the Charter, domestic law must recognise her the right to reinstatement. The lack of this consequence in national regulation leads to the declaration of its non-conformity with the Charter. It should be underlined that non-conformity remains even if national law, under these circumstances, grants women an economic compensation. In fact, the provision of a compensation is not enough. Reinstatement must be the rule. Therefore, when analysing Albanian national law, the ECSR concluded that it was not in conformity with article § 8.2 because “reinstatement is not the rule in cases of dismissals on the grounds of pregnancy or maternity leave (after childbirth) in the private sector”⁹⁴. Also in Conclusions 2011, but regarding Finnish legislation, the ECSR decided for non-conformity. In its report, Finland had clarified that, although legislation did not ensure women reinstatement in case of unlawful dismissal during pregnancy or maternity leave, an agreement could be struck between employer and employee to consider

⁸⁶ Conclusions 2011, Armenia.

⁸⁷ Conclusions 2019, Montenegro.

⁸⁸ Conclusions 2015, Lithuania; Conclusions 2005, Estonia. According to Irish domestic law, “dismissals are unfair if they result wholly or mainly from the employee’s pregnancy, or matters connected with it, unless the employee, by reason of her pregnancy or matters connected with it, was unable (i) to perform adequately the work for which she was employed, or (ii) to continue to do her work without contravention of a statutory requirement by her employer, (iii) and her employer had no other suitable vacancy to offer at the time of the dismissal, or (iv) she refused an offer for a suitable alternative job in order to keep her employed, notwithstanding her pregnancy. It also noted that discrimination based on pregnancy was covered by the Employment Equality Act”. Nevertheless, the ECSR asked for further information on how such legislation “interacted in the event of the dismissal of a pregnant woman and how the relevant authorities and courts interpreted them”, since such situations seem to go beyond the exceptions acceptable under article § 8.2 (Conclusions 2019, Ireland).

⁸⁹ Conclusions 2011, Italy.

⁹⁰ Conclusions XIX-4, Poland; Conclusions 2011, Armenia.

⁹¹ Conclusions 2011, Lithuania.

⁹² Conclusions 2011, Armenia.

⁹³ Conclusions XIX-4, Poland.

⁹⁴ Conclusions 2011 and 2019, Albania.

the dismissal null and void. In spite of that, the ECSR considered that such a solution was not a sufficient safeguard to fulfil the requirement of article § 8.2⁹⁵.

2. Compensation

Whenever unlawful dismissal occurs overpassing the prohibition dictated by article § 8.2 of the Charter and women refuse reinstatement, or it simply is not possible (e.g. the enterprise has closed down), they must have the right to a financial compensation. If domestic law does not regulate the right to a compensation in case of unlawful dismissal related with these circumstances, it shall be considered as non-conform to the Charter⁹⁶.

This compensation assumes a double goal: 1) compensate the women victims of dismissal for the loss suffered; 2) discourage employers from adopting this type of behaviour. Thus, it must be proportionate to the victim's injury and sufficiently dissuasive for employers⁹⁷. Compensation shall attend both the loss of employment and the finding of new employment⁹⁸.

In order to ensure the achievement of these aims, national legislations cannot introduce any ceiling on the level of compensation. The existence of a ceiling could preclude damages from being totally commensurate or hinder the desired deterrent power of the compensation. This interpretation of the ECSR come with dissenting opinions⁹⁹.

As a result, after 2011, the ECSR loosened the criteria of compliance slightly. Now, the existence of an upper ceiling is not automatically considered a contravention of article § 8.2 of the Charter¹⁰⁰. Actually, if the ECSR detects a ceiling for pecuniary damage, the conformity of the domestic law with article § 8.2 depends on the fact that the victim can seek compensation for non-pecuniary damage through other legal avenues (e.g. anti-discrimination legislation)¹⁰¹. In this situation, it is also required that the competent courts decide within a reasonable time¹⁰².

III. § 8.3 – RIGHT TO TIME OFF FOR NURSING

This article has its origins in article § 8.3 of the Charter of 1961. It was maintained, with no modifications, in the Revised Charter. Similar time off rights for nursing can be found in article 10 of ILO Maternity Protection Convention No. 183.

⁹⁵ The same was determined in ECSR, Conclusions 2019, Finland. Although reinstatement in cases of unlawful dismissal now covers, in the public sector, civil servants at the State and Municipal level, and the Evangelical Lutheran Church of Finland, legislation still does not provide for the right to reinstatement in case of unlawful dismissal in the private sector, even if an agreement can be reached between employer and employee to consider the dismissal null and void.

⁹⁶ ECSR, Conclusions 2017, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Turkey.

⁹⁷ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on article § 8.2.

⁹⁸ Matti MIKKOLA, *Social Human Rights*, Karelactio, 2010, p. 455.

⁹⁹ See Dissenting opinion by Monika Schlachter on Article § 8.2 concerning the following States: Luxembourg, Poland, Lithuania, Slovenia, Turkey (Conclusions 2011): "For achieving a deterring effect the established consequences must be sufficiently severe and the likelihood to face such consequences must be substantial. The effect, however, will not be determined by the composition of elements of payments due. If the amount of money that has to be awarded is high in absolute terms, the mere existence of an upper limit will not destroy the deterring effect. Whenever an employer has to award a substantial amount of money to the wrongfully dismissed former employee for which the recipient doesn't have to work, such deterring effect will be achieved. Therefore I conclude that the Committee should not judge the compliance with the said Charter provisions on the mere existence of an upper limit for compensation in national law but should assess the likelihood of a deterring effect by taking into consideration the amount that a wrongfully dismissed former employee could be awarded in absolute terms".

¹⁰⁰ See Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 320.

¹⁰¹ Conclusions 2019, Bulgaria, Albania and Turkey. Regarding Italy (Conclusions 2019), the ECSR considered that the right of the employee to "choose between reinstatement and compensation in lieu amounting to 15 months' actual total salary" is not in conformity with the Charter "on the grounds that adequate compensation may not be awarded in case of unlawful dismissal during pregnancy or maternity leave if the woman concerned does not wish to be reinstated".

¹⁰² Conclusions XIX-4 and Conclusions 2011, Statement of Interpretation on article § 8.2.

A. PERSONAL SCOPE

Time off for mothers who are nursing their infants must be given to all women employed in both the private and public sectors¹⁰³.

Regarding different types of employment contracts, the ECSR has highlighted that domestic employees, as well as women working at home¹⁰⁴, are included¹⁰⁵. The same applies to fixed-term employees¹⁰⁶ and women working part-time, although in this last case an adaptation according to a proportionality principle can be applied¹⁰⁷.

B. NURSING DEFINITION

A first doubt that might arise regards the concept of nursing. Should it be interpreted as including only breastfeeding, or can it also take in situations of bottle feeding?

As it happens in ILO regulation¹⁰⁸ and in EU Law¹⁰⁹, it seems like this special protection is exclusive to breastfeeding women. In other words, to women who feed their babies with breast milk rather than with formula milk from a bottle. In fact, the ECSR, in its conclusions, consistently refers to employed mothers who *breastfeed* their babies¹¹⁰.

The explanation for this is probably related with the fact that article § 8.3 establishes a singular protection for women (and not for men). If a child is fed in an alternative way to breastfeeding, men can perform that task. Consequently, the different treatment of both parents in this situation could infringe the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards working conditions¹¹¹.

Some domestic laws grant a larger protection to employees, which is naturally considered in conformity with the Charter. For example, in Cyprus employees have the right to reduce their daily working time in one hour until the child is nine months old, whether they are nursing their infant or not. This time is considered as working time and is remunerated as such¹¹².

¹⁰³ ECSR, Conclusions XXI-4, Spain; Conclusions 2011 and 2019, France; The ECSR concluded that French domestic law was not in conformity with article § 8.3 of the Charter since women working in the civil service were not entitled to breastfeeding breaks.

¹⁰⁴ This reference to women working at home might expand the scope of this provision to workers, and not only employees.

¹⁰⁵ ECSR, Conclusions 2019, Italy. For further developments, see point D *infra* – Sufficient time off for nursing.

¹⁰⁶ Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Montenegro.

¹⁰⁷ ECSR, Conclusions 2019, Portugal. Still, in this case, a minimum period of 30 minutes is established for part-time employees.

¹⁰⁸ Article 10 of ILO Convention No. 183: “1 – A woman shall be provided with the right to one or more daily breaks or a daily reduction of hours of work to breastfeed her child. 2 – The period during which nursing breaks or the reduction of daily hours of work are allowed, their number, the duration of nursing breaks and the procedures for the reduction of daily hours of work shall be determined by national law and practice. These breaks or the reduction of daily hours of work shall be counted as working time and remunerated accordingly”.

¹⁰⁹ Council Directive 92/85/EEC.

¹¹⁰ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 118, as well as in several of its conclusions (e.g. Conclusions 2019, Italy).

¹¹¹ This problem was analysed by the CJEU, 30 September 2010, *Pedro Manuel Roca Álvarez v. Sesa Start España ETT SA*, C-104/09, regarding the company’s refusal to accord Roca Álvarez a so-called nursing leave, which could also be granted in cases of bottle feeding. The CJEU noted that the leave had been detached from the biological fact of breastfeeding, so that it could be considered as time purely devoted to the child and as a measure that reconciled family life and work following maternity leave. Therefore, “the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions, must be interpreted as precluding a national measure such as the one at issue in the main proceedings, which provides that female workers who are mothers and whose status is that of an employed person are entitled, in various ways, to take leave during the first nine months following the child’s birth, whereas male workers who are fathers with that same status are not entitled to the same leave unless the child’s mother is also an employed person”.

¹¹² ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Cyprus.

C. INFANT AGE

It is the ECSR's understanding that breastfeeding breaks shall be granted at least until the child reaches the age of nine months¹¹³.

However, breaks may be reduced over the course of the nine months. That is, for instance, the case of Slovakia, where women are entitled two half-hours nursing breaks per shift (for each child) until the child reaches six months of age and, in the succeeding six months, one half-hour break per shift (for each child)¹¹⁴.

Regarding Bulgarian domestic law, the ECSR deferred its conclusions on (non)conformity, since after the child reaches eight months of age, breaks only exist where the medical authorities find that it is necessary for the woman to continue to breastfeed the child. Therefore, the ECSR considered that a conformity declaration should depend on the information about whether in practice women wishing to continue breastfeeding their child over eight months were granted the necessary certificate from the medical authorities¹¹⁵. In response, the Bulgarian report of 2019 explains “that employers have no discretion in such cases and are obliged to comply with the prescriptions of the medical authorities”. Thus, the ECSR considered that the situation is in conformity on this point¹¹⁶.

D. SUFFICIENT TIME OFF FOR NURSING

All employed women shall be entitled sufficient time off for nursing. The ECSR has been very flexible when appreciating what is considered “sufficient time” for these breaks. In fact, several different solutions have been declared as in conformity with article § 8.3. Each situation is assessed on a case-by-case basis, since the length of the pauses “varies between countries and is frequently combined with specific solutions”¹¹⁷.

For instance, in Andorra's domestic law¹¹⁸, women employed in the public sector can be absent for two hours a day, which may be divided into two one-hour periods, so as to care for a child under nine months of age, during a period of not more than six months. These periods of time off may be accumulated in a single period of paid leave, equivalent to 40 days, from the end of maternity leave, a solution that has been considered in conformity with article § 8.3.

In Ukraine, “employed women with children under 18 months are entitled to take nursing breaks of at least 30 minutes (60 minutes in case of two or more children) at intervals of three hours (...)”. Regarding the schedule and modalities for these breaks, they are defined “by the employer or an organisation authorised by the employer, in cooperation with trade union representatives of the enterprise concerned, and taking into consideration the mother's wishes”¹¹⁹. A similar regime can be found in Latvian law, where breaks for nursing may also be added to regular work breaks or, if so requested by the employee, transferred to the end of the day, shortening the length of the working day¹²⁰. The same option is provided in Azerbaijan legislation, where women are granted 30 minutes break every three hours (for two or more children breaks will be of at least one hour each) to feed children under the age of 18 months¹²¹.

¹¹³ ECSR, Conclusions 2007, Armenia.

¹¹⁴ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Slovakia.

¹¹⁵ Conclusions 2011, Bulgaria.

¹¹⁶ Conclusions 2019, Bulgaria.

¹¹⁷ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 321. See also Matti MIKKOLA, *cit.*, pp. 458-459.

¹¹⁸ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Andorra.

¹¹⁹ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Ukraine.

¹²⁰ ECSR, Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Latvia.

¹²¹ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Azerbaijan.

In the Slovak Republic, the number of nursing breaks is set based on the length of the working day. Women working less than half of the statutory working time, for instance two full working days twice a week, are entitled to two breaks for each day¹²². Several models of part-time work (shortening the workday) can also be accepted, as long as they do not involve a pay reduction or, otherwise, “loss of income is compensated by parental benefit or other allowance”¹²³.

All these diverse solutions were considered in conformity with article § 8.3, provided that these periods are treated as working time and remunerated as such.

E. TIME OFF PAYMENT

Nursing breaks must be granted during working hours and treated as normal working time, including being remunerated as such.

The non-remuneration of this time off is reason enough for the ECSR to consider domestic law in non-conformity with the Charter. For instance, the ECSR concluded that French law was not in conformity with article § 8.3 of the Charter because the remuneration of breastfeeding breaks was not guaranteed to employed women covered by the Labour Code¹²⁴.

Also, Italian domestic law was considered as non-conform to article § 8.3 of the Charter. The detected problem was that workers and home workers were not entitled to paid breaks for the purposes of breastfeeding their infants¹²⁵. Even though domestic workers had the possibility to reach an agreement with their employer on remunerated breaks, that was not considered sufficient by the ECSR¹²⁶.

Nevertheless, the ECSR has accepted that the mere provision for part time work could fulfil the purposes of article § 8.3, provided the loss of income be compensated by a parental benefit or other allowance¹²⁷. That is the case of Sweden’s legislation, in which women nursing their children can reduce their daily working time and the loss of income is compensated by parental benefits¹²⁸.

IV. § 8.4 – EMPLOYMENT OF PREGNANT WOMEN, WOMEN WHO HAVE RECENTLY GIVEN BIRTH AND WOMEN NURSING THEIR INFANTS IN NIGHT WORK

A. SCOPE AND PURPOSE

¹²² ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Slovak Republic.

¹²³ Matti MIKKOLA, *cit.*, p. 459. The Author further explains the evolution of the ECSR case law regarding Sweden on this matter from non-conformity to conformity with the Charter.

¹²⁴ Conclusions 2011 and 2019, France.

¹²⁵ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Italy. More recently, in Conclusions 2019, Italy argued that the payment of home workers is “based on piece rates, without reference to an hourly or monthly wage”. Therefore, “since remuneration is based not on hours worked but on piece rates, it is impossible to calculate the share of working time corresponding to breaks, with the result that the legislation on nursing breaks cannot apply to this category of women workers”.

¹²⁶ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Italy. More recently, in Conclusions 2019, the Representative of Italy highlighted “a distinction between two scenarios in this respect: 1) if the employee works full time with the employer’s family, she may take nursing breaks in the context of the organisation of her working time and these will be remunerated; 2) if she works part-time for several employers, arrangements for nursing breaks shall be left to the discretion of the parties, bearing in mind the relationship of trust inherent in this type of work”. The ECSR asked what guarantees are in place to ensure full-time domestic workers are entitled to paid nursing breaks and deferred its conclusion pending receipt of the information requested.

¹²⁷ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Serbia.

¹²⁸ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Sweden.

According to § 8.4, the Parties undertake to regulate the employment of pregnant women on night work, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants.

This paragraph has its origins in article § 8.4(a) of the Charter of 1961: “With a view to ensuring the effective exercise of the right of employed women to protection, the Contracting Parties undertake to regulate the employment of women workers on night work in industrial employment”. When interpreting article § 8.4(a) of the Charter of 1961, the ECSR declared that the scope of such regulation was “to limit the adverse effects of night work on the worker’s health and family life and to prevent abuses”¹²⁹.

The revised Charter, on the one hand, enlarged the protection to employed women in all sectors (and not only in industry) and, on the other hand, specified that the protection is intended, not to all women, but only to pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants¹³⁰. Otherwise, we would be facing discrimination based on sex, as explained above in the Introduction. Therefore, the reason behind the modification of § 8.4 is “treating men equality with women where possible”¹³¹. As far as other women are concerned, they are protected, as well as men, by article § 2.7, requiring “that workers performing night work benefit from measures which take account of the special nature of the work”¹³².

This different approach had taken into account ILO Convention No. 171 (1991), regulating night work, as well as Council Directive 92/85/EEC (article 7)¹³³.

The aim is now narrowed to limiting the adverse effects of night work on the health of these women (pregnant, who have recently given birth and nursing)¹³⁴, along with, as more recently the ECSR clarified¹³⁵, the protection of the health of the child (unborn or new-born). Such protection depends on the assurance of safe and healthy working conditions, i.e. “working conditions which take due regard to their specific needs during respective periods”¹³⁶.

Moreover, following the reasoning of the CJEU¹³⁷, the ECSR has made clear that safe and healthy working conditions must include “protection against less favourable treatment due to pregnancy and maternity”. This means that, since pregnancy and maternity are gender-specific, any less favourable treatment due to these circumstances is to be considered as direct sex discrimination. Therefore, “the non-provision of specific rights aimed at protecting the health and safety of a mother and a child during pregnancy and maternity, or the erosion of their rights due to special protection during such a period, are also direct sex discrimination”¹³⁸.

Regarding the definition of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants, the reference is Directive 92/85/EEC (article 2)¹³⁹, which admittedly inspired the

¹²⁹ Conclusions X-2, Statement of interpretation on article § 8.4.

¹³⁰ Article § 8.4 requires some form of protection for women as long as they are breastfeeding their children, even beyond the end of the statutory maternity leave period, as stated by the ESCR, Conclusions 2003, France.

¹³¹ David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, p. 264. As Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 322, puts it, this change “eliminates discrimination in two directions. First, women are not excluded from jobs that, though more demanding, may offer better earnings and career opportunities. Second, men shall enjoy equal – equally better! – protection with women against obvious harms and dangers that previously were considered properly addressed by the exclusion of women from those jobs”.

¹³² See David HARRIS / John DARCY, *cit.*, p. 263.

¹³³ See Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3.V.1996, p. 6.

¹³⁴ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119.

¹³⁵ Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹³⁶ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹³⁷ See Introduction.

¹³⁸ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹³⁹ “For the purposes of this Directive: (a) pregnant worker shall mean a pregnant worker who informs her employer of her condition, in accordance with national legislation and/or national practice; (b) worker who has recently given birth shall mean a worker who has recently given birth within the meaning of national legislation and/or national practice and who informs her employer of her condition, in accordance with that legislation and/or practice; (c) worker who is breastfeeding shall mean a worker who is breastfeeding within the meaning of national legislation and/or national practice and who informs her employer of her condition, in accordance with that legislation and/or practice”.

interpretation of article 8 of the Charter¹⁴⁰. Besides, as previously mentioned, the ECSR takes account of the law of the EU when interpreting the Charter¹⁴¹. Still, although the Directive refers to “national legislation and/or national practice” for the definition content, this reference cannot narrow the personal scope of § 8.4. For instance, it would not be admissible for such reference to exclude women having recently given birth who do not breastfeed¹⁴². The problem regarding the definition of “women having recently given birth” was addressed in the context of § 8.5 of the Charter. The ECSR considered that it is up to the States’ Parties to define it in national law. However, women who do not breastfeed but have recently given birth must be protected. Consequently, in 2011, Bulgarian legislation was declared as non-conform to article § 8.5 of the Charter because women who had recently given birth, but were not breastfeeding, did not benefit from the possibility of adjustments to their working conditions, nor from temporary reassignment to an adequate post¹⁴³.

With regard to these categories of women, all who have a paid employment are protected, including civil servants. Only self-employed women are excluded¹⁴⁴.

B. NIGHT WORK DEFINITION

The definition of the night work frame is left to national laws. Similarly to what we have seen for breastfeeding breaks, here too the ECSR has acknowledged a variety of solutions.

For instance, the ECSR has accepted the following night work frames: between 8.00pm and 5.00am (in the summer and 6.00am during winter)¹⁴⁵; between 10.00 pm and 6.00 am¹⁴⁶; between 8pm and 7am¹⁴⁷; between 8 pm and 6 am¹⁴⁸.

C. NIGHT WORK REGULATION

In order to comply with the goals of article § 8.4, night work does not need to be prohibited for pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants, it only needs to be regulated in order to limit the adverse effects on the health of these women¹⁴⁹. That is the reason why Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina legislation was declared by the ECSR in non-conformity with article § 8.4 of the Charter, since night work of pregnant women, women having recently given birth and women nursing their infants was not regulated¹⁵⁰.

According to the ECSR, night work shall only be authorized where necessary, “having due regard to working conditions and the organisation of work in the firm concerned”¹⁵¹.

Furthermore, domestic laws must stipulate special conditions for night work of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants, such as “prior authorisation by the Labour Inspectorate (when applicable), prescribed working hours, breaks, rest days following periods of

¹⁴⁰ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, pp. 49-50; Explanatory Report to the European Social Charter (Revised), Strasbourg, 3.V.1996, p. 6.

¹⁴¹ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, pp. 49-50.

¹⁴² Conclusions 2011, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

¹⁴³ Conclusions 2017, Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. See, also, Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 323.

¹⁴⁴ Conclusions 2011, Bulgaria.

¹⁴⁵ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119, referring directly to article § 8.5.

¹⁴⁶ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Albania.

¹⁴⁷ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Armenia, and Conclusions 2015, Latvia.

¹⁴⁸ ECSR, Conclusions 2011, Portugal.

¹⁴⁹ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Austria.

¹⁵⁰ ECSR, Conclusions 2015, Georgia; Conclusions 2011, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

¹⁵¹ Conclusions 2017, Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

¹⁵² Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119.

night work, the right to be transferred to daytime work in case of health problems linked to night work, etc.”¹⁵².

For example, regarding Armenian law, the ECSR began by issuing a declaration of non-conformity and, after Armenia amended its legislation, it considered that it was in conformity with the Charter. In fact, in its 2011 Conclusions, the ECSR found out that employees working at night were subject to a pre-entry medical examination and periodical medical examinations. The ECSR thought it was crucial to know whether the compulsory medical examination had to take place not only upon recruitment, but whenever a pregnant woman, a woman having recently given birth, or breastfeeding her child was assigned to night work, and whether those periodic medical check-ups were also mandatory afterwards. Otherwise, Armenian legislation could not be declared as conforming with article § 8.4 of the Charter¹⁵³. In 2017, after being informed that Armenian law had been amended in order to require a medical exam and the submission of its results to the employer in all cases where a pregnant woman or a woman taking care of a child under the age of three has to perform night work, when an employee performing night work becomes pregnant, or when she returns to night work following maternity leave, the ECSR concluded with a conformity statement¹⁵⁴.

D. EXEMPTION FROM NIGHT WORK

If pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants are exempted from performing night work, it is necessary, in order to ensure non-discrimination on the grounds of gender, to ensure that these women are not placed in a less advantageous situation due to this exemption (see above point IV.A)¹⁵⁵.

Following similar criteria as the ones defined in article 7 of Council Directive 92/85/EEC¹⁵⁶, the ECSR required some positive measures. Firstly, “an adjustment of their working conditions in order to ensure the required level of the protection of health”, which can imply transfer to daytime work, including another work post. Secondly, if such transfer is not possible, they should be granted a leave from work. In both cases, their income shall not be affected. Therefore, “during the protected period, she is entitled to her average previous pay or provided with a social security benefit corresponding to 100% of her previous average pay”. Additionally, she has the right to return to her previous post when the health reasons disappear or at the end of the protection period¹⁵⁷.

For example, in its 2015 Conclusions, the ECSR noted that in Montenegro employees who were pregnant or had a child under three years old could not perform night work. Exceptionally, an employed woman with a child over two years of age might do it, but only if she accepts it in a written statement. In this scenario, the ECSR asked for clarifications about what happens to women who do not perform night

¹⁵² Conclusions X-2 (1990), Statement of Interpretation on Article § 8.4; Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119.

¹⁵³ Conclusions 2011, Armenia.

¹⁵⁴ Conclusions 2017, Armenia.

¹⁵⁵ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹⁵⁶ “1. Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that workers referred to in Article 2 are not obliged to perform night work during their pregnancy and for a period following childbirth which shall be determined by the national authority competent for safety and health, subject to submission, in accordance with the procedures laid down by the Member States, of a medical certificate stating that this is necessary for the safety or health of the worker concerned. 2. The measures referred to in paragraph 1 must entail the possibility, in accordance with national legislation and/or national practice, of: (a) transfer to daytime work; or (b) leave from work or extension of maternity leave where such a transfer is not technically and/or objectively feasible or cannot reasonably be required on duly substantiated grounds”.

¹⁵⁷ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

work, in particular if they are transferred to daytime work until their child is three years old, and what rules apply if such transfer is not possible¹⁵⁸.

V. § 8.5 – EMPLOYMENT OF PREGNANT WOMEN, WOMEN WHO HAVE RECENTLY GIVEN BIRTH AND WOMEN NURSING THEIR INFANTS IN UNSUITABLE WORK, BY REASON OF ITS DANGEROUS, UNHEALTHY OR ARDUOUS NATURE

A. SCOPE AND PURPOSE

Article § 8.4(b) of the Charter of 1961 determined that: “With a view to ensuring the effective exercise of the right of employed women to protection, the Contracting Parties undertake to prohibit the employment of women workers in underground mining, and, as appropriate, on all other work which is unsuitable for them by reason of its dangerous, unhealthy, or arduous nature”. This means that, in its origin, the prohibition to perform a dangerous, unhealthy, or arduous work was addressed to all women. However, in its Statement of interpretation on the old § 8.4, the ECSR stated that the prohibition of employment of women in the above-mentioned occupations should be limited “to the sole cases where this is necessary, in particular to protect motherhood, notably pregnancy, confinement and the post-natal period, as well as future children”¹⁵⁹.

Similarly to what happened with article § 8.4(a), the prohibition’s scope of application was amended in the Revised Charter. Article § 8.4.b has given place to article § 8.5, establishing that its prohibition only applies to pregnant women, women who have recently given birth or who are nursing their infants. The purpose is to protect the employment rights of these women, in particular to safeguard their (and their foetuses/children) safety and health¹⁶⁰, avoiding sex discrimination issues.

As referred above, the ECSR issued a common Statement of Interpretation on both articles § 8.4 and § 8.5, according to which safe and healthy working conditions must include “protection against less favourable treatment due to pregnancy and maternity”. Therefore, “the non-provision of specific rights aimed at protecting the health and safety of a mother and a child during pregnancy and maternity, or the erosion of their rights due to special protection during such a period are also direct gender discrimination”¹⁶¹.

The personal and material scope of article § 8.5 is identical to that of article § 8.4, to which we refer.

The personal scope of the underground mining work prohibition will be addressed in the following point.

B. PROHIBITED ACTIVITIES

Under article § 8.5 of the Charter, pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women who are nursing their infants must be prohibited from working in underground mining. The scope, as we have seen, is to protect safety and health of women and their foetuses/children. Therefore, it is not necessary to prohibit those categories of women from performing all kinds of works related with underground mining. What must be prohibited is performing the extraction work. Consequently, it is the ECSR’s opinion that the provision does not apply to women who: a) “occupy managerial posts and do

¹⁵⁸ Conclusions 2015, Montenegro.

¹⁵⁹ Conclusions X-2 - Statement of interpretation on article § 8.4.

¹⁶⁰ Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, p. 5-6).

¹⁶¹ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, p. 5-6). See also commentary IV. § 8.4.

not perform manual work”; b) “work in health and welfare services”; and c) “spend brief training periods in underground sections of mines”¹⁶².

Besides work in underground mining, article § 8.5 also refers “all other work which is unsuitable by reason of its dangerous, unhealthy or arduous nature”, and which includes activities which imply exposure to lead, benzene, ionizing radiation, high temperatures, vibration, or viral agents¹⁶³. Nevertheless, this is not a closed list. States’ Parties must ensure a high level of protection against all known hazards to the health and safety of women, prohibiting or strictly regulating all activities capable of raising them. These activities can either be totally prohibited or only strictly regulated. It will depend on the risks posed by the work¹⁶⁴.

For example, the ECSR considered that the legislation of Bosnia and Herzegovina was not in conformity with article § 8.5 of the Charter, because it did not prohibit or strictly regulate the work of pregnant women, women who are nursing their infants and women who have recently given birth in dangerous activities such as those involving exposure to lead, benzene, ionizing radiation, high temperatures, vibration, or viral agents¹⁶⁵. Georgia’s domestic law was also declared as non-conform with article § 8.5, since, although it prohibited the employment of pregnant or nursing women in dangerous, unhealthy, and arduous work, it had adopted no detailed regulation to materialize that protection¹⁶⁶.

C. MEASURES OF PROTECTION

Whenever pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and women nursing their infants perform an activity that raises risks to their, or to their child’s, safety and health, they must be reassigned to another hazard-free work post.

In line with EU law, the measures to be adopted in this regard are the same mentioned in the subject of night work exemption (see point IV.D). In order to ensure non-discrimination on the grounds of gender, these women cannot be placed in a less advantageous situation due to such reassignment¹⁶⁷. Therefore, this modification cannot imply a loss of pay.

If reassignment is impossible, women must be entitled to paid leave. Also in this situation, their income cannot be affected: “during the protected period, she is entitled to her average previous pay or provided with a social security benefit corresponding to 100% of her previous average pay”¹⁶⁸. As soon as women lose their special condition, they have the right to return to their previous employment/work post¹⁶⁹.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

As stated above, the protection of pregnant women, women who have recently given birth and breastfeeding women within the labour market is the outcome of a virtuous circle of reciprocal interactions between the ESC (rev), the United Nations Treaties (particularly, under ILO) and EU law¹⁷⁰. It is likely that this reciprocity and synergy continues to foster broader interpretations of article 8 of the Charter.

¹⁶² Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119; Conclusions 2015, Hungary,

¹⁶³ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119.

¹⁶⁴ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119; Conclusions 2017, Azerbaijan; Conclusions 2017, Georgia.

¹⁶⁵ Conclusions 2015 and 2019, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

¹⁶⁶ Conclusions 2017 And 2019, Georgia.

¹⁶⁷ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹⁶⁸ ECSR, Statement of Interpretation on Articles § 8.4 and § 8.5 (Conclusions 2019, General Introduction, pp. 5-6).

¹⁶⁹ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, p. 119; Conclusions 2007, Albania; Conclusions 2015, Azerbaijan, Russia and Serbia; Conclusions 2017 and 2019, Georgia.

¹⁷⁰ Csilla KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, *cit.*, p. 325, speaks about “a triangular and constant flow of interactions”.

In fact, EU law is evolving from a traditional approach to maternity issues towards an approach that also includes paternity issues and, more broadly, reconciliation of family and working life topics¹⁷¹. After recognizing that maternity provisions involve not only a problem of women's health and safety, but a challenge to gender equality, the new EU legislation is progressing towards an integrated approach of maternity and paternity protection and balanced reconciliation of work and family life as a material requirement for gender equality at work¹⁷².

This integrated approach can be perceived in article § 33.2 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights, which mentions maternity and paternity rights and the right to the reconciliation of family and working life¹⁷³. Furthermore, the recent Directive (EU) 2019/1158 on work-life balance for parents and carers¹⁷⁴ – one of the first initiatives aimed at promoting the European Pillar of Social Rights, specifically its principles 2 (Gender equality) and 9 (Work-life balance), as well as part of the development of the EU Strategic Engagement for Gender Equality (2016-2019) – adopts a broader scope, as well as the explicit formalization, in article 1, of the link between reconciliation and equality between men and women with regard to labour market opportunities and treatment at work. Additionally, the evolution of an EU concept of worker¹⁷⁵, also concerning Directive 92/85/EEC¹⁷⁶, may influence the personal scope of article 8 of the Charter.

Remembering what has been said regarding the ECSR taking account of EU law when interpreting the Charter¹⁷⁷, this evolution can impact its case law regarding article 8, challenging the ECSR with new interpretation perspectives.

Biographical Notes

Catarina de Oliveira Carvalho

PhD in Labour Law. Associate Professor at Porto Faculty of Law, Universidade Católica Portuguesa. Researcher at Católica Research Centre for the Future of Law (CEID). Vice-General Coordinator of the Academic Network on European Social Charter and Social Rights (ANESC). Member of IR Share Network – Industrial Relations Share. Board member of the Portuguese Association of Labour Law (APODIT). President Arbitrator in the Arbitration Tribunal of the Economic and Social Council. Participation in several European projects related to the implementation of the EU Labour Law. Author of several publications in Labour and Civil Law, namely “Concilier vie professionnelle et vie familiale pour promouvoir l'égalité femmes-hommes au Portugal: perspectives à la lumière de la Directive 2019/1158”, *Revue de Droit Comparé du Travail et de la Sécurité Sociale*, No. 3, 2020, pp. 82-93 ; “Trabalho no domicílio, trabalho doméstico e trabalhos de cuidado no ordenamento jurídico português: primeira leitura à luz das Convenções da OIT”, *Documentación Laboral*, No. 116, 2019, pp. 41-56.

¹⁷¹ Maria do Rosário Palma RAMALHO, *cit.*, p. 11.

¹⁷² This “integrated approach” is explained and upheld by Maria do Rosário Palma RAMALHO, *cit.*, pp. 11 ff.

¹⁷³ Maria do Rosário Palma RAMALHO, *cit.*, p. 12.

¹⁷⁴ This new Directive builds on the rules laid down in the previous Directive 2010/18/EU of 8 March implementing the revised Framework Agreement on parental leave concluded by BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP and ETUC and repealing Directive 96/34/EC.

¹⁷⁵ See, namely, Stefano GIUBBONI, “La Nozione Comunitaria di Lavoratore Subordinato”, in Silvana SCIARRA/ Bruno CARUSO (eds.) *Il Lavoro Subordinato*, Turino, Giappichelli Editore, 2009, pp. 35 ff.

¹⁷⁶ E.g. CJUE, 11 November 2010, *Dita Danosa*, C-232/09.

¹⁷⁷ Digest of the case law of the ECSR, December 2018, pp. 49-50.

Luísa Andias Gonçalves

Degree in Law by the Faculty of Law of the University of Coimbra, Master in Legal and Business Sciences by the Faculty of Law of the University of Coimbra, PhD in Labour and Social Labour, by the Faculty of Law of the University of Salamanca. Professor at the School of Technology and Management, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria. Invited lecturer in the Master in Law at the Oporto Law School of Portuguese Catholic University. Member of the Portuguese section of RACSE-ANESC. Author of “A redução do valor das pensões à luz do artigo 1.º, do Protocolo n.º 1, da Convenção Europeia dos Direitos do Homem”, *Lex Social*, Vol. 7, 2017, pp. 141-156, and “Reflexões em torno da reforma das prestações sociais – das pensões em especial”, in *Por onde vai o Estado Social em Portugal?*, Vida Económica, 2014, pp. 189-214.

Bibliography

CARVALHO, Catarina Oliveira, “Informações Relativas ao Estado de Gravidez e (Não) Contratação de Trabalhadora Grávida para o Exercício de Actividades Proibidas ou Condicionadas Face à Jurisprudência do Tribunal de Justiça das Comunidades Europeias (TJCE)”, in *O Direito Material e Processual do Trabalho dos Novos Tempos – Estudos em Homenagem ao Professor Estêvão Mallet*, São Paulo, LTr, 2009, pp. 94-108.

GIUBBONI, Stefano. “La Nozione Comunitaria di Lavoratore Subordinato”, in Silvana SCIARRA/ Bruno CARUSO (eds.) *Il Lavoro Subordinato*, Turino, Giappichelli Editore, 2009, pp. 35-75.

GOMIEN, Donna/ HARRIS, David/ ZWAAK, Leo. *Convention Européenne des Droits de l’Homme et Charte Social Européenne: Droit et Pratique*, Strasbourg, Éditions du Conseil de l’Europe, 1997.

HARRIS, David/ DARCY, John. *The European Social Charter*, 2nd Edition, New York, Transnational Publishers, 2001.

KOLLONAY-LEHOCZKY, Csilla. “The Right of Women to Maternity Protection”, in Niklas BRUNN, et al. (eds.) *The Employment Social Charter and the Employment Relationship*, Oxford and Portland, Hart Publishing, 2017, pp. 307-326.

LUKAS, Karin. *The Revised European Social Charter – An Article by Article Commentary*, Camberley, Edward Elgar Publishing, 2021.

MIKKOLA, Matti. *Social Human Rights*, Karelactio, 2010.

RAMALHO, Maria do Rosário Palma. “Reconciling Family and Professional Life and the Gender Equality Principle in Employment”, *European Gender Equality Law Review*, no. 2, 2009, pp. 7-14.

VALTICOS, Nicolas. *Derecho Internacional del Trabajo*, Madrid, Tecnos, 1977.